

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Mauno, S. (2024). Coping with Technostress in the Software Industry: Coping Strategies and Factors Underlying their Selection (Online Replication Package) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14180104>

For how long did the experience last?	Percent	Number	How long ago did the experience occur?	Percent	Number	How would you evaluate the strain caused by the experience?	Percent	Number
Less than one hour	6.2%	44	Less than two weeks ago	16.6%	119	Very high	38.7%	277
1–12 hours	26.7%	191	2–4 weeks ago	14.1%	101	Fairly high	39.7%	284
13–24 hours	8.7%	62	1–3 months ago	20.6%	147	Moderate	21.5%	154
1–7 days	22.7%	162	4–12 months ago	21.5%	154	Fairly low*	4.8%	34
1–4 weeks	15.8%	113	Over one year ago	26.3%	188	Very low*	1.1%	8
Over one month	18.3%	131	I don't know	0.8%	6	I don't know*	0.3%	2
I don't know	1.7%	12				*Excluded from analysis		